

Periodontics Redefined: Trailblazing Breakthroughs in Artificial Intelligence (AI)

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Abstract

Periodontal diseases, which include gingivitis and periodontitis, are inflammatory conditions affecting the supporting structures of teeth, with multifactorial etiology involving microbial, genetic, and systemic factors. Accurate diagnosis, risk assessment, and treatment planning remain challenging in complex conditions, like periodontitis. Artificial intelligence (AI) offers promising solutions in periodontics through machine learning, deep learning, and convolutional neural networks, enabling early disease detection, prediction of progression, and treatment planning. AI applications include periodontal disease classification, radiographic analysis, implant planning, and patient education. Integration of AI support for clinicians in delivering precise, patient-centered periodontal care while fostering interdisciplinary collaboration can open the doors to great avenues in terms of precision dentistry.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Periodontics, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Dental Diagnostics

Introduction

Periodontal diseases, encompassing gingivitis and periodontitis, are characterized by inflammation and destruction of the supporting structures of the teeth. Globally, it affects millions of individuals and is ranked as the sixth most prevalent health condition.¹ The etiological factors that precipitate the above-mentioned conditions, particularly gingivitis, are primarily attributed to plaque biofilm accumulation on tooth surfaces, hence resulting in inflammation of the gingiva, which is completely reversible by oral hygiene practices and professional oral prophylaxis. However, if left untreated, gingivitis might progress to periodontitis, which is considered to be triggered due to multifactorial conditions like genetic, smoking, systemic diseases like diabetes, etc.²

Two key factors in understanding and managing this complex disease include (i) approaching the disease, which is quite challenging because of its multifactorial etiology that complicates accurate diagnosis and risk assessment. (ii) The introduction of the 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-Implant Diseases and Conditions, which replaced the previously recognized terms like chronic and aggressive periodontitis with a staging and grading system. Although the new classification has provided an extensive framework, it has also

generated considerable confusion amongst periodontists regarding the interpretation of the disease severity and progression. Moreover, extensive data points and longitudinal studies are required to understand the status of periodontal disease.^{2,3}

At present, the integration of health care with technology has been widely embraced and has remarkably led to enhanced diagnostics and improved treatment, and patient care. In the pursuit of improved periodontal care, technological advances like incorporating artificial intelligence have become paramount.¹ While Artificial Intelligence (AI) has found widespread applications across various domains of medicine and dentistry, its adoption in periodontics remains relatively sparse.² Therefore, this review focuses on highlighting periodontitis from an artificial intelligence (AI) perspective.

Definition: AI is a popular buzzword in technology that deals with the science of teaching a computer, computer-assisted robot, or a software program to process information and make decisions like the human brain.⁴ **It is defined as “The branch of science and engineering associated with computational knowledge which is commonly referred to as intelligent behavior, as well as the development of systems exhibiting similar behavior.”²**

Timeline of Artificial Intelligence Development and Applications in Dentistry¹

1. 1950 – Turing Test (Imitation Game)

Alan Turing, an English mathematician, proposed this concept to evaluate whether a machine could demonstrate human-like intelligence.

2. 1955 – First AI Program Published

Allen Newell and Herbert Simon introduced the first AI program

3. 1956 – Dartmouth Conference

John McCarthy officially coined the term “**Artificial Intelligence**” at this conference, making history.

4. **1959 – Introduction of “Machine Learning”**

Arthur Samuel introduced the concept and coined the term “**Machine Learning**,” marking a core concept of AI.

5. **1970–1980 – First AI Winter**

A period that slowed AI development due to unmet expectations and technological limitations.

6. **1980–1987 – Rise of Expert Systems**

Expert systems emerged, enabling AI programs to solve domain-specific problems using knowledge-based logical rules, leading to increased funding.

7. **Late 1980s–Early 1990s – Second AI Winter**

Another decline in AI research occurred due to financial setbacks

8. **1995 – Early AI in Oral Medicine**

Speight et al. proposed the use of AI for assessing oral cancer risk, marking one of the early applications of AI in dentistry.

9. **May 11, 1997 – Deep Blue’s Historic Win**

IBM’s Deep Blue defeated the reigning world chess champion, Garry Kasparov, becoming the first computer program to do so.

10. **Early 2000s – Data and Computing Revolution**

Rapid AI advancements are occurring across industries, including healthcare and dentistry.

11. **2016 – Orthodontic AI Applications**

Jung and Kim developed an artificial neural network to analyze the need for orthodontic extractions, demonstrating AI’s clinical decision-making potential.

12. **2018 – AI in Clinical Decision Support & Imaging**

13. **Thanathornwong et al.** created an AI-based clinical decision support system.

14. **Patcas et al.** applied convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for orthodontic treatment outcome analysis.
15. **Nam Y, Kim HG et al.** utilized natural language processing (NLP) to convert patient symptoms and histories of TMJ disorders into computable data, leading to the development of an AI-enabled diagnostic system.

Classification of AI⁵

AI can be implemented in various approaches, and different types of AI are capable of performing different tasks.

1. **Machine learning and deep learning** – learn from data and make predictions, and can also recognize patterns
2. **Natural Language programming (NLP)**- computers interpret and understand, and also generate in human language
3. **Expert systems** – use the “if and then” concept for decision making, similar to humans
4. **Recognition of speech**- recognize and speak human language
5. **Robotics**- Machines performing tasks on command or autonomously
6. **Vision and planning** – interpret visual data (e.g., radiographs/ photographs) and arrive at a decision

Machine Learning and Deep Learning: The Core of Modern AI in Periodontics ¹

Machine learning (ML): This component of the algorithm focuses on predicting outcomes from the provided database by identifying new information and patterns, thereby adapting them to generate results without human intervention. E.g., ML can be applied in diagnosing and managing periodontitis by relying on analyzing large datasets to predict disease progression, assess risk factors, and also generate a treatment plan.

Deep learning (DL): This component is a part of ML that mimics the human brain, not by strictly following the algorithm that is pre-programmed, but by understanding the core structure of the dataset provided. The dataset is designed to develop a neural network that

efficiently and automatically recognizes patterns, thereby facilitating improved detection in the future. E.g., data in the form of images, radiographs, or 3D scans can detect bone loss and patterns in periodontal diseases with high accuracy

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN): A Neural network is a subset of artificial intelligence modeled to function similarly to the human brain. These networks consist of interconnected artificial neurons that process clinical, radiographic, and demographic data to identify complex patterns and relationships that may not be easily discernible by human evaluation alone.

Convolutional neural network (CNN): This is a subset of ANN that works by replicating the visual cortex and hence handles imaging data. E.g., CNN facility can compare the pre- and post-treatment images to assess tissue regeneration, hence providing an objective evaluation of the treatment outcome.⁶

Mechanisms of Artificial Intelligence: It consists of 2 phases.¹

- a) **Training phase:** Teaching the AI in terms of characteristics, patterns, and associations in the form of datasets and algorithms. The whole purpose is to train the AI to make accurate predictions and decisions.
- b) **Testing phase:** This phase is the part where the trained AI Draws conclusions based on fresh data that is provided, which were not a part of the training phase.

Table 1: Role of Artificial Intelligence in Periodontics

S.no	Purpose	Author, year, and study	AI used	Findings
1.	Classification of periodontal diseases	Feres et al 2018⁷ 40 bacterial species were used to classify patients, using AI, into Generalized chronic periodontitis, Generalized aggressive	Support vector machine-based differentiation (Machine learning)	This Support vector machine-based differentiation using a panel of 40 species successfully distinguished between Generalized chronic periodontitis, Generalized

		periodontitis, and periodontal health.		aggressive periodontitis, and periodontal health
2.	Detection of periodontal disease	Lee et al, 2013⁸ Used AI to diagnose and predict periodontally compromised teeth (PCT) with the help of IOPA (intraoral periapical radiographs) of 64 molars and 64 premolars	Deep learning (DL)-based convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm	The authors concluded that using DI-CNN was useful to draw up PCT with an accuracy of 81.0 %for premolars and 76.7 % for molars.
3.	Periodontal risk assessment (PRA)	Ossowska, A et al 2022⁹ Used AI to assess the grades of periodontitis in the group of patients. Gender, age, nicotine use, Plaque Index, bleeding on probing, clinical attachment loss, and pocket depth were taken into consideration.	Artificial neural networks (ANN)	This retrospective study showed an accuracy of 84.2%, sensitivity of 85.7% and specificity of 80.0% and may be a useful tool in everyday practice to assess the risk of periodontal disease.
4.	AI-driven treatment planning	Mangano FG et al 2023¹⁰ Provided a novel protocol for planning a guided implant placement using an	Machine learning	The authors concluded that time-efficient and effective planning was possible using this technology of combining intra-oral scanner and

		intra-oral scanner and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), artificial intelligence, and augmented reality		cone beam computed tomography, artificial intelligence, and augmented reality, and hence, the accuracy of the implant placed was acceptable
5.	AI in patient management and follow-up	Krois J et al. 2019¹¹ Used panoramic radiographs to assess the percentage of bone levels by using 2001 image segments by AI, and compared the results with six dentists	Deep learning (DL)-based convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm	There were no statistically significant differences wherein the mean accuracy by CNN was 0.81, and that of the dentists was 0.76. hence suggesting that AI-based machines and deep learning can be used to make decisions in a time-efficient manner.
6.	Detection of halitosis	Nakhleh et al. 2017¹² Collected breath samples from 1,404 subjects. A nanoarray composed of modified gold nanoparticles and a random network of single-walled carbon nanotubes was used to noninvasively diagnose and classify multiple diseases from exhaled breath.	Machine learning	The result suggests that the approach is promising, with 86% accuracy for non-invasive diagnosis.

7.	Use of AI in dental implant treatment planning	Morgan et al 2022¹³ Used CBCT images to segment anatomical boundaries of the maxillary sinus, generating precise 3-D anatomical models	Deep learning (DL)-based convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm	The approach proved to be time-efficient, clinically reliable, and highly applicable for diagnostic purposes and implant placement (e.g., sinus lift procedures).
8.	AI in the detection of implant type	da Mata Santos et al., 2021¹⁴ Used AI to identify implant brands using periapical radiographs	Deep learning (DL)-based convolutional neural network (CNN) algorithm	The AI system demonstrated high diagnostic precision by achieving an accuracy of 85.29% in identifying implant type and manufacturers.
9.	Haptics-Based Virtual Reality Periodontal Training Simulator	Steinberg et al, 2007¹⁵ developed a haptic/virtual-reality dental simulator that incorporates recording and playback of trainee performance to allow students to practice, review, and refine their motor skills	Because of the era (2007) the system is not described as “deep learning” or “machine learning classifier” but rather a training simulator with feedback/recording capabilities	The simulator improved training outcomes, shortened lessons, improved the learning curve, and allowed unlimited practice
10.	Chat-generative pre-trained transformer (ChatGPT) in periodontology	Alan et al. 2023¹⁶ Conducted a study to evaluate the quality of information generated by ChatGPT-4	Deep learning (DL)	ChatGPT provided mostly accurate and consistent responses about periodontal disease. However, the model showed limitations in

		regarding periodontal disease (PD)		delivering detailed, evidence-based clinical recommendations, particularly regarding treatment selection and individualized patient care.
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Advantages:¹

1. High diagnostic accuracy by achieving high sensitivity and specificity
2. Standardization of treatment protocol
3. Systematic data management systems that allow structured collection of patient data, analysis, and interpretation.
4. Minimize human error and reduce bias during diagnosis and decision making
5. Time efficient
6. Enhanced patient communication – AI-driven tools can aid in patient education and engagement.

Limitations:¹

- 1) High cost of implementation
- 2) Requirement for large, high-quality datasets for training AI algorithms.
- 3) Data privacy and security concerns raise ethical and legal problems.
- 4) AI operates with logical reasoning and lacks empathy, and hence needs constant human surveillance.

Conclusion:

To conclude, AI tools hold a promising position in revolutionizing the field of periodontics, enabling early detection of the disease and bone loss, better understanding of risk factors,

and assisting clinicians in formulating precise, evidence-based treatment plans. Despite the limitations, ongoing research and technological advancements constantly work on improving the pitfalls that arise with the technology. By embracing the technology, we can establish opportunities for an interdisciplinary approach that can provide precision in periodontal care. Notwithstanding that AI can never replace clinicians but the support can open doors for a holistic patient and clinician-centered healthcare system.⁶

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